

THE IMPORTANCE OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS WHILE CHOOSING METHODOLOGIES FOR CONDUCTING READING LITERACY LESSONS IN PRIMARY CLASSES

Otamirzaeva K.I.

Doctoral student, Namangan State University

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the topic “The importance of a teacher’s pedagogical skills in choosing a method for conducting reading literacy lessons in primary school.” The demands of today require future teachers to keep up with the times and always use their scientific potential, creativity, and work tirelessly on themselves. For this reason, the intellectualization of the educational process is one of the pressing problems of modern pedagogy.*

Keywords: *methodology, method, method, potential, interactive, graphic organizers, intelligent, interactive educational strategies.*

INTRODUCTION

It is not a secret that the Republic of Uzbekistan stands out as a developing country with a bright future. For establishing a strong foundation for its future and ensure that the future generation grows up educated and mature in all aspects, the country is making many reforms and changes in the education system.

It is known that the 21st century is called the century of the information society. In all periods of social development, the intellectualization of the education system was considered a requirement of the time. The modern process of education and learning requires teachers to have a perfect command of intellectual knowledge, potential and ways of transmitting it to students. But it is impossible to do this with old methods and tools.

As the President of our Republic Sh.M. Mirziyoev suggested: “At present time in order to renew and modernize our country, its development on an innovative basis, the implementation of the multifaceted and complex tasks that we set for ourselves, we need modern and creative thinking in any situation. We entrust important tasks in state and public administration to young patriotic personnel who are able to take responsibility, have enthusiasm, and have high intellectual potential.”

The demands of today require future teachers to keep up with the times and always use their scientific potential, creativity, and work tirelessly on themselves. For this reason, the organization of the educational process by teachers who have pedagogical skills and their training are one of the pressing problems of modern pedagogy.

LITERARY REVIEW:

It is important to suggest that pedagogical skill has a certain methodological basis as a science about the professional and personal qualities of a teacher-educator. In fact, scientific-theoretical, methodological and practical directions for the formation of professional skills of a teacher were developed by Yu.P. Azarov, T.I. Gonobolin, A.K. Kuzmina, O.A. Abdulina, A.V. Mudrik, N.V. Kukharev, V.A. Tselestionin, V.A. Kan-Kalik, N.D. Nikandrov, A.V. Petrovsky, Umar az Zamakhshari, Burhaniddin Zamuji, Abu Nasr Farabi, Ibn Sina, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Alisher Navoi, M. Ochilov, K. Zaripov, V.A. Krutetsky, Yu.G. Yoldoshev, E. Gaziev, U. Makhkamov, B.

Khodzhaev, A. Khalikov and others are covered in scientific works. According to Ulama, a teacher should be knowledgeable in his field, be humane, fair, contribute to national education, have a profession that includes personal and professional qualities as a perfect person.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.

The article examines the importance of a teacher's pedagogical skills when choosing a method for conducting reading literacy classes in elementary school. In particular, the features of the "Two-Part Diary" and "Joint Table" methods are described.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

A teacher with high pedagogical skill can select interactive methods suitable for any topic and, through the selected methods, convey the topic being taught to students in understandable and fluent language. In every society, the most important task of teachers and educators is to educate young people who are the future of society. Currently, the number of creative teachers is increasing every year, who, with their dedicated work, contribute to improving the quality of education and upbringing of the younger generation.

Interactive methods are explained by the following specific aspects:

1. Interactive methods are based on active interaction between teacher and student, full explanation of each other.
2. The main goal of introducing interactive methods into the educational process is to ensure cooperation between teacher and student in the lesson, in whatever form it takes, wherever it is held.
3. In this case, the teacher acts only as a leader (manager, observer, conclusion).
4. Due to these methods, students develop independent thinking skills, laying the foundation for the development of free thinking, independent decision-making, the ability to manage emotions, critical and creative thinking.

The essence of teaching using interactive methods is as follows:

- both the teacher and the student actively work with information;
- encourages students to think independently;
- serves the teacher to "teach students to think", and serves students "to learn to think."

Method "Two-part diary". "Two-part diary" is a pedagogical method that develops written speech. This method allows you to connect the concepts of the topic being studied with personal experience. We will use this method while reading the story "Izza" by Muhabbat Khamidova, given in Part IV of the textbook "Reading Literacy" for 3rd grade.

It is recommended to use the method in the consolidation part of the lesson.

Step 1: Students take turns reading the text aloud in pairs.

Step 2: Make sure everyone has read the text and ask them to divide the notebook in half with a vertical line.

Step 3: Students are asked to write down what they like (or don't like) about the author's comments on the left side of their notebook.

Step 4: On the right side, the reader writes his own explanation of this thought, that is, he summarizes his understanding of the text read.

Step 5: At the end of this part of the assignment, students are asked to read (optional) one idea and one commentary written about them. You are allowed to ask questions or comment on this opinion while reading the opinions and comments on them. Step 6: Students can also work in pairs (triads or small groups).

Goal: to cultivate patriotic qualities in students. Interpret the example of patriotism as an example for students. It is to develop students' written language.

Objective: students' ability to independently work on the text and draw the necessary conclusions from the topic is developed.

Oyi	The helper of a mother	
Axl	Is it a sin to throw garbage into water?	
Suv	The importance of water	
Suv	Water is food for many	
	Our duty is to save water	
	Who is nature's friend?	

Definitely, in Polat Momin's poem "Ishlagan Charchai", which is given in the 2nd topic of section IV of the textbook "Reading Literacy" for 2nd grade. If we use the following Joint method, shown in the Table, there will be provided more information about careers and develop students' critical thinking skills and independent work skills.

The condition of the task is to find and write the names of such professions, the last syllable of which ends with the syllable -er in the center. You should inform us what professions you found.

CONCLUSIONS.

From the above-mentioned ideas, it should be concluded that any skillfully chosen method cannot, but contribute to the development of students. Therefore, based on the advanced pedagogical experience of developed countries from relevant sources, theoretical information about the delivery of the necessary knowledge and skills to primary school students through innovative technologies, methods, methods and techniques was studied. While teaching curriculum subjects, it is necessary to consider on what topics it is advisable to organize interactive lessons. This involves the use of interactive or traditional modes of teaching to ensure that the learning objectives for each topic are fully achieved. For interactive learning to be effective, it is necessary to ensure that students know the basic concepts and preliminary information on its topic before new training. It must be taken into account that students spend more time on independent work during interactive learning than during traditional learning.

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